

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE AMELIORATIVE EFFECT OF A COMBINATION OF VITAMIN C AND ACTIVATED CHARCOAL ON PARAQUAT-INDUCED KIDNEY TOXICITY IN WISTAR RATS

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Abstract: The aim of this work is to investigate the ameliorative effect and the safety of Vitamin C/ Activated Charcoal combination on Paraquat-induced kidney histopathology and normal kidney of Wistar rats respectively. Also, to investigate the relationship between the level of tissue damage and clinical manifestations with the duration of paraquat exposure. The work was carried out at the National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom, Nigeria, from March 1st to March 28th, 2025. A total of 40 female 8 week old Wistar rats, weighing between 150 to 200 grams were used. They were randomly assigned into 4 groups, of 10 rats each. Group 1 rats, normal control, received orally, 1ml of normal saline solution daily for 28 days. Group 2 animals received paraquat solution at 50mg/kg body weight dissolved in 1ml of distilled water once daily, for 28 days. Group 3 animals received paraquat solution at 50mg/kg body weight daily, followed after 5 minutes by 1ml of a combination of a solution of Vitamin C at 250mg/ kg body weight and a suspension of activated charcoal in distilled water at 0.175g/kg body weight, once daily for 28 days. Group 4 animals were administered 1ml of a combination of a solution of Vitamin C at 250mg/ kg body weight and a suspension of activated charcoal in distilled water at 0.175g/kg body weight once daily for 28 days. They

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Glomerular atrophy, Kidney tubular hypertrophy

were observed weekly. Kidney tissue was harvested weekly for histopathology processing and microscopic examination from the groups randomly. The histopathological method applied is tissue morphology assessment and intra as well as extra cellular substances manifestation. Groups 1 and 4 kidney tissue showed normal morphology throughout the experiment. Group 2 animals showed massive tissue necrosis, interstitial haemorrhage, glomerular atrophy and tubular dilatations which worsens with the duration of the experiment. Group 3 kidney, microscopically showed mild tubular hypertrophy on day 7, a sign of signifying recovery. However, for days 14, 21 and 28, group 3 kidney showed mild tissue degeneration, dilatation of the tubules and tubular atrophy. This means that the combination is effective in ameliorating paraquat-induced nephrotoxicity but continues exposure of the toxicant overwhelms the efficacy of this combination. An adjustment of the combination and the dosage would be a greater help in future studies. The maintenance of normal tissue architecture in group 4 throughout the experiment has shown that at this dosage and duration, the combination is safe on the kidney. Other organs can be investigated for safety of the combination too.

Introduction

Vitamin C (Ascorbic acid) is a water-soluble essential vitamin with antioxidant properties found in both animals and plants but cannot be synthesized by humans and must be obtained from the diet (Carr and Maggin, 2017; Okolonkwo, 2022). This compound has antioxidant potentials and readily scavenge reactive oxygen and nitrogen species which are associated with lipid peroxidation, damage of DNA, and proteins (Vissers and Das, 2018). Vitamin C is a free radical scavenger and also has antioxidant action based on other mechanisms within the system, including the activation of intracellular antioxidant systems and its effect on the NFκB/TNFα pathway and apoptosis (Mazurek and Pankiewicz, 2012; Ang et al., 2018). Vitamin C has different mechanisms of boosting immunity including: improvement of chemotaxis (or leukocyte migration); neutrophilic phagocytosis and oxidative killing; attenuation of the neutrophil extracellular trap

formation (NETosis) and reduction of the uncontrollable inflammatory cytokine production in the alveolar space; differentiation and proliferation of B and T-lymphocytes; antibody production; cortisol production; interferon-γ production; downregulation of interleukin (IL) -6 and endothelin-1; increased lung epithelial barrier; susceptibility and outcome of low respiratory tract infections (Neeth et al., 2022; Mortaz et al., 2021). Vitamin C has been used in combination with different compounds, to mitigate toxicity caused by various agents whether from within the system or from exogenous sources (Vetvicka, and Vetvickova, (2012).

Activated charcoal (AC) is an odorless, tasteless, and very fine black powder that acts as an “adsorbent” for poisons, gases, toxicants, and several impurities. It has been widely applied for medicinal, veterinary, and aquatic medical purposes as a “universal antidotal treatment” for several poisons and environmental toxicants and

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is on the World Health Organisation's List of Essential Medicines (Boonanuntanasarn et al., 2014; World Health Organization, 2023). The mechanisms of actions of AC showed its potential in vitro affinity in the adsorption and elimination of several toxicants such as aflatoxins and pesticide tissue residues (Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2017). Activated charcoal is manufactured by heating common charcoal in the presence of a gas which causes the charcoal to develop lots of internal spaces or "pores." These pores help activated charcoal "trap" chemicals. Activated charcoal is used for the treatment of poisonings, reduction of intestinal gas (flatulence), lowering of cholesterol levels, preventing hangover, and treatment of bile flow problems (cholestasis) during pregnancy (Olson, 2010). The normal dosage consists of an amount which is 10 to 40 times as much as that of the intoxicating substance, or else 0.5-1 g/kg body weight in children or 50 g in adults. Repeated application is indicated for intoxications with agents that persist for a longer time in the stomach and for intoxications with timed-release drugs or drugs with a marked enterohepatic or entero-enteric circulation (Zellner et al., 2019). Activated charcoal has a very large surface area and porous structure, allowing it to physically adsorb a wide range of chemicals, drugs, and toxins in the gastrointestinal tract. Apart from the physical adsorption phenomenon, the porous structure of activated charcoal is also helpful because of its negative electrical charge. It pulls

positively charged toxins and gases. These molecules are then trapped inside the intricate meshwork of crevices and holes in the activated charcoal (Hassen, and Abdulkadir, 2022). This prevents these substances from being absorbed into the bloodstream and reduces their systemic effects.

Paraquat, also known as methyl viologen, is a quaternary compound whose characteristics were first described in 1993 by Michales and Hill and has a high herbicidal property (Kim and Kim, 2020; Dinis-Oliveira et al., 2008). It was introduced as an herbicidal agent into the market in August 1962 by Imperial Chemical industries, now Syngenta (Khodayar et al., 2014; Roberts et al., 2002). This liquid herbicide was primarily used for weed and grass control but due to its highly poisonous nature was soon categorized as a "restricted-use" herbicide (Wesseling et al., 2005). When either accidentally, intentionally or maliciously ingested, paraquat selectively accumulates in the lungs resulting in the production of oxygen-free radicals, resulting in membrane damage and cell death (Okolonkwo et al., 2023). Ingestion of even a very small quantity of paraquat, with delayed intervention can cause severe multiorgan dysfunction and death (Mehta et al., 2025). Although a substantial amount of research has been produced on paraquat intoxication for most developed countries, there are research gaps regarding the international research agenda in this research area (Baradaran Rahimi et al., 2019; Jain et al., 2022). The lung

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and the kidney are the main target of paraquat toxicity. Research has proven that paraquat cytotoxicity occurs in the mitochondria and particularly in mitochondrial-rich tissues (Griffin et al., 2002). Paraquat is also actively secreted by the kidney leading to its accumulation in the proximal tubular epithelial cells at higher concentrations. The mechanisms of the toxic effects of paraquat are largely the result of a metabolically catalyzed single electron oxidation reduction reaction, resulting in depletion of cellular NADPH and the generation of potentially toxic forms of oxygen such as the superoxide radical (Shimada et al., 2009).

The aim of this work is to assess the efficacy of a combination of Vitamin C and Activated charcoal as an ameliorative agent against paraquat-induced renal toxicity in Wistar rats. The work will also investigate the relationship between the severities of paraquat histotoxicity in relation to duration of exposure. The work will also investigate the safety of this combination on the kidney of Wistar rats so as to open way for compounding different formulations of the combination for better results.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Location

This research work was conducted at National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom, Plateau state, latitude 9° 53' N, and longitude 8° 51' E, an altitude of 1,217m above sea level (National Population Commission, 2006).

Ethical consideration

Ethical Clearance was obtained from the National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom, Animal Ethics Committee (AEC), where they gave an Animal Ethics Number AEC/02/173/24 after an application and a thorough interview, before the commencement of the work with periodic unannounced visits to the experimental station by members of the ethics committee, until the termination of the experiment.

Experimental Animals

A total number of 40 female 8 week old Wistar rats that weigh between 150 to 200 grams were obtained from the small animal Experimental station of the National Veterinary Research institute (NVRI) Vom, Plateau State, Nigeria, and used for the experiment. All experimental activities were carried out conformity with internationally acceptable guidelines on the ethical use of experimental animals in research (Haripriya et al., 2017; Reddy et al., 2019). The rats were housed in the Animal Experimental station of the Federal College of Veterinary and Medical Laboratory Technology, NVRI, Vom in cages during the experiment period (Edo, 2022; Ijaz et al., 2023). The rats were allowed to adjust in accordance with favorable conditions for two (2) weeks that would allow them to adapt to their new environment and fed with a standard grower's mash obtained from Grand Cereal Ltd and water to meet the nutritional requirements for growth and maintenance in rats (Lewis et al., 2006). The constant environmental condition was maintained with proper ventilation and a

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good source of light (12h light -12h dark and 20°C ± 30°C) (Nwafor et al., 2020) with free access to food and water (Amin et al., 2025). Excrement and spillage were changed frequently (Reed et al., 2011). A veterinarian ascertained the health status of as well as provided care and ensure the health of the laboratory animals throughout the experiment so as to maintain a standard experimental protocol (Debnath et al., 2024; Pedroso et al., 2025). Animals were divided into 4 groups of 10 animals each.

Chemical and treatment compounds sources

Paraquat was purchased under the trade name 'KINGRAMO', from Agricultural Services and Training Centre, Vom Station, Jos Plateau State. Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) was obtained from Lamed Pharmacy Ltd, Jos under the brand name 'Nature's Field Vitamin C 1000mg, manufactured by Bactolac Pharmaceuticals Incorporated, USA (Lot 2503034). Activated charcoal was obtained from Lamed Pharmacy Ltd, Jos under the brand name 'Kunimed Activated Charcoal Powder Anti-poison' (Batch number KAC10). Distilled water and deionised water were obtained from the Cell culture Laboratory of the Viral Vaccine production Division, National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom.

Experimental Design

The rats were randomly assigned into 4 groups, containing 10 rats each. Group 1 served as normal control were exposed to normal

atmospheric and nutritional condition, and received 1ml of normal saline solution daily (0.9% NaCl) throughout the experiment period (Hernandez-Baixauli, et al., 2024). Group 2 animals were administered paraquat solution at 50mg/kg body weight dissolved in 1ml of distilled water once daily, for 28 days. Group 3 animals were administered paraquat solution at 50mg/kg body weight daily, followed after 5 minutes by 1ml of a combination of a solution of Vitamin C at 250mg/ kg body weight and a suspension of activated charcoal in distilled water at 0.175g/kg body weight, once daily for 28 days. Group 4 animals were administered 1ml of a combination of a solution of Vitamin C at 250mg/ kg body weight and a suspension of activated charcoal in distilled water at 0.175g/kg body weight, once daily for 28 days. All solutions of the compounds were administered via oral gavage route. Although activated charcoal can bind some of the vitamin C and reduce its efficacy, the activated charcoal also binds the paraquat hence a significant quantity of the vitamin C will still be available to perform its antioxidant ability. The dose of Paraquat was chosen to model occupational exposure to paraquat. Doses of Activated Charcoal and Vitamin C were chosen based on previous related studies (Reddy et al., 2019).

Procedure for paraquat and treatment solutions administration

The rats were held at the skin over the head and turned so that the mouth was faced upward and

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the body lowered towards the holder. The syringe needle bevel was then placed into the mouth of the rat a bit laterally in a way to avoid the teeth which are located centrally. The content in the syringe was then emptied into the mouth of the rat gradually (Okolonkwo, 2022)

Experimental Protocol

Animals were observed before and after the administration of the Paraquat solution across the treatments groups (Turner et al., 2011). During the experimental period, clinical signs and behaviors of all rats such as physical activity, diarrhea, tremor, paralysis, food/water consumption, injury and death were monitored daily. At the end of the each week (that is, day 7, day 14, day 21 and day 28), animals from each group were randomly selected, and sacrificed by cervical dislocation after 12 hours of fasting. The Kidneys were observed, harvested and fixed immediately in 10% buffered formalin, for histopathology processing (Adefola et al., 2024).

Histopathological Processing and Evaluation: Tissues (Kidney) from all groups were subjected to standard routine histopathological procedures, using the conventional paraffin wax method (Avwioro, 2011), embedded, sectioned and stained using the haematoxylin and Eosin Staining technique (Choji et al., 2015). They were read microscopically: A commercially available web camera (QHM495 LM, Shenzhen Hiper Song Electronic Limited, Hong Kong, China) with complementary metal oxide semiconductor

sensor which yield interpolated 25 mega pixel images was used for micrograph capture after slide reading and interpretation (Mondal et al., 2019)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was designed to study, microscopically, the ameliorative effect of a combination of Vitamin C and activated charcoal on Paraquat-induced kidney toxicity in Wistar rats at definite time intervals in different groups, alongside clinical signs. This approach was aimed at studying what happens at cellular level, when vitamin C and Activated charcoal are combined in an effort to ameliorate renal toxicity caused by paraquat oral exposure.

CLINICAL SIGNS

Clinical signs and behaviors of all rats such as physical activity, diarrhea, tremor, paralysis, food/water consumption, injury and death were observed daily across the groups, with group 1 and 4 showing normal physical presentation and feed consumption. Severe reduction in feed/water intake, respiratory distress, Squeaking sound and generalized weakness of the body, anorexia and bloody nasal discharges were observed in group 2 animals especially as from day 12 to 28, with 3 mortalities, one recorded on each of day 8, day 17 and day 25. Group 3 animals, showed mild weakness of the body, mild reduction in feed consumption and respiratory distress, especially from the 7th to 14th day, with no bloody nasal discharge and are more active

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compared to group 2 animals. There was one mortality recorded in group 3 on day 23.

Histopathology

The Kidney from groups 1 and 4, microscopically, shows normal morphology throughout the

experiment, with clearly defined Kidney architecture, while morphological variation manifest across the groups as seen in the photomicrographs.

Plate 1: Kidney of Wistar rat from the four groups on day 7. Group 1, 3 and 4 show normal histology. The glomerular tufts (white stars) are normal in architecture and surrounded by clear capsular spaces. The tubules (white arrows) are normal.

The glomerular capsules (black arrowheads) present their characteristic simple squamous epithelium. However, there is hypertrophy of the glomeruli in group 3, evident by the conspicuous loss of capsular spaces. The tubules in group 3

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are hypertrophied, evident by the reduction in interstitial spaces. In group 2, there is massive tubular necrosis (stars) and inter tubular

haemorrhage (black arrows), glomerular atrophy (white stars) leading to increased capsular space.

H&E X100

Plate 2: Kidney of Wistar rat from the four groups on day 14. Group 1, 3 and 4 show normal histology: the glomerular tufts (white stars) show normal architecture and surrounded by clear capsular spaces and intact glomerular capsule, showing the characteristic simple squamous epithelial cell. The tubules (white

arrows) are normal in groups 1 and 4 while they look hypertrophied in group 3 (white arrowheads). Group 2 shows tubular degeneration (necrosis) and loss of tubular epithelium (black stars) with dilated tubules (black arrows). **H & E X100**

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Plate 3: Kidney of Wistar rat from the four groups on day 21. Groups 1 and 4 show normal morphology with glomerular tufts (white stars) showing normal architecture and surrounded by clear capsular spaces. The tubules (white arrows) are normal. The glomerular capsules (black arrowheads) present their characteristic simple

squamous epithelium. Group 2 shows hypertrophy and extravasated blood cells (haemorrhage) (black arrows). The glomerular tufts (white stars) are hypertrophied. Group 3 shows tubular degeneration (necrosis) (black stars) with tubular dilatation (white arrows) **H&E X100.**

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Plate 4: Kidney of Wistar rat from the four groups on day 28. Groups 1 and 4 show normal morphology with glomerular tufts (white stars) showing normal architecture and surrounded by clear capsular spaces. The tubules (white arrows) are normal. The glomerular capsules (black arrowheads) present their characteristic simple squamous epithelium. In group 2 and 3, there is massive tubular necrosis (stars) and, glomerular atrophy (white stars) leading to increased

capsular space, with conspicuous tubular dilatation (black arrows). **H&E X100**

Conclusion

Paraquat has continuously been used in developing countries, including Nigeria, despite its toxic effect on the ecosystem. As a result of its toxicity on Humans and animals, it is either highly restricted or completely banned, in many developed countries across the world (Akram, 2014). It is therefore, of great concern, especially as the world focuses on the one health concept,

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covering the three components of Human, animal and environmental health. Though other organs have been found to be affected by paraquat intoxication regardless of the route of exposure, the lung and the kidney are the main target of paraquat toxicity (Griffin et al., 2002). Paraquat is also actively secreted by the kidney leading to its accumulation in the proximal tubular epithelial cells at higher concentrations, distorting cellular integrity of the renal architecture, especially the glomeruli and tubular tissues (Okolonkwo et al., 2014). The mechanisms of the toxic effects of paraquat are largely the generation of potentially toxic forms of oxygen such as the superoxide radical (Shimada et al., 2009) hence a need to find an antioxidant in its amelioration. Here, vitamin C comes handy. Vitamin C has been shown to neutralize the free radicals produced following PQ exposure (Awadalla, 2012; Choudhary et al., 2025). Histological study on the ameliorative effect of the combination of Vitamin C and activated charcoal on the kidney of Wistar rats was carried out to see if the combination would ameliorate Paraquat-induced toxicity on the kidney to fill the gap in the quest for finding an antidote against paraquat toxicity (Zhang et al., 2019). It is also aimed at investigating the safety of the combination, so as to create a pathway for further studies, using the same combination. Activated charcoal has been used either as a single compound or in combination with other compounds to manage paraquat toxicity (Wang

et al., 2015) but it has not been combined with Vitamin C.

Kidney microscopic architecture in Groups 1 and 4 remained histologically normal throughout the experiment, while group 2 and 3 present different morphological outlook, from day 7, to day 28. On the 7, group 2 kidney show massive degeneration of the kidney, with intertubular haemorrhage, while group 3 shows hypertrophy of the glomeruli and tubules. This is an evidence of recovery and agrees with the physical behavior of the animals, who were physically stable, with normal consumption of feed and water, in comparison with group 2 animals that shows weakness of the body, general reduction in feed and water consumption, Paralysis, bloody nasal discharges as well as respiratory distress. On day 14, Kidneys of group 2 animals show massive degeneration and tubular degeneration while that of group 3 are hypertrophied, an evident of recovery which agrees with other research work previously done (Akinloye and Arowolo, 2011). On days 21 and 28 (plates 3 and 4 respectively), the kidneys in group 2 and 3 show similar presentation of tubular degeneration (necrosis) with tubular dilatation. This shows that with extended duration of exposure, the toxicity of paraquat on the kidney overwhelms the ameliorative effect of the combination of vitamin C and activated charcoal. This agrees with other researchers who found out that when the system is overwhelmed by paraquat toxicity, the

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protective effect of vitamin C combination is reduced, leading to organ damage (Kivrak et al., 2017). Group 2 recorded 3 mortalities, one on each of day 8, day 17 and day 25, while group 3 recorded 1 mortality on day 23. This research has shown that the combination of Vitamin C and Activated charcoal, gives a good result in ameliorating paraquat toxicity. It agrees with the work done by Choji, et al., 2026 where this combination showed ameliorating effect on paraquat-induced toxicity in the lungs of Wistar rats. Further work on adjustment of the dosage is recommended. Also, since activated charcoal is an adsorbent, it is possible it interferes with some portions of the activated vitamin C, thereby reducing its efficacy. It is recommended that in

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future work, the administration of the two substances should not be concurrent or the vitamin can be administered via other routes apart from the oral route, while the activated charcoal is administered via the oral route.

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